

Effect of fertilizers and green manure on yield of detached deepwater rice plants grown in water.

Treatment	Yield (g m ⁻² tank area)	
	Grain	Straw
No fertilizer (control)	14.4	261
5 ppm N as urea	25.1	321
10 ppm N as urea	27.4	329
5 ppm N through fresh <i>Sesbania aculeata</i> plants (3 kg)	22.6	326
5 ppm N as urea and 5 ppm P ₂ O ₅ as single superphosphate	37.5	394
5 ppm N as urea, 5 ppm P ₂ O ₅ as single superphosphate, and 5 ppm K ₂ O as muriate of potash	38.7	378
LSD (0.05)	6.9	39.5

of N alone, either through urea or green manure. The detached plants could complete their life cycle to grain filling and ripening without anchorage and nutrition from the soil. However, grain yield was low, with a maximum harvest index of 0.1. ■

Integrated N management with *Gliricidia maculata* and *Sesbania aculeata* for transplanted rice

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To save on fertilizer costs, green manure (GM) is used in conjunction with fertilizer N. We evaluated the effect of integrating GM *Gliricidia maculata* and *Sesbania aculeata* with different levels of fertilizer N (urea) on grain yield of transplanted rice in the 1989-90 rainy season. *Gliricidia* seedlings were planted on ricefield bunds at a distance of 0.5-1 m. The plants produced sufficient green loppings after 3 yr with 2.74% N, 0.5% P, and 1.1 % K in the leaves (dry weight basis). *Sesbania* was grown in situ at a seeding rate of 50 kg ha⁻¹ and incorporated in the soil after 45 d. *Sesbania* contained 2.9% N, 0.2% P, and 0.98% K. Soil was clay with pH 8.1, 0.6% organic C, and 200-42-346 kg available NPK ha⁻¹.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. GM crops were incorporated in the soil at transplanting. On the same day, 30-

Effect of green manure and fertilizer N on rice yield and comparative economic data. Maharashtra, India.

Treatment	Rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Cost of cultivation (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	Gross returns (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	Net returns (US\$ ha ⁻¹)	B:C ^a
	1989	1990	Pooled mean				
100 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea in 3 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/4 at tillering + 1/4 at panicle initiation (recommended)	3.6	2.6	3.1	344.99	404.71	59.72	1.17
5 t <i>G. maculata</i> ha ⁻¹ (27.4 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 50 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.1	2.2	2.6	330.10	342.95	12.85	1.04
7.5 t <i>G. maculata</i> ha ⁻¹ (41.1 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 25 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.4	2.5	2.9	334.80	385.00	50.20	1.15
5 t <i>S. aculeata</i> ha ⁻¹ (29 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 50 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.2	2.3	2.8	335.70	363.98	28.28	1.08
7.5 t <i>S. aculeata</i> ha ⁻¹ (43.5 kg N ha ⁻¹) + 25 kg N ha ⁻¹ as urea at planting	3.4	2.1	2.7	333.35	357.41	24.06	1.07
Control (no N)	2.4	1.5	1.9	301.46	253.60	-47.86	0.84
SE±	0.2	0.2	0.1				
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.5	0.2				

^aBenefit-cost ratio.

to 35-d-old seedlings of 125-d-duration rice variety PLG1 were transplanted. P and K at 50 kg ha⁻¹ each were basally applied. N was applied as per treatment schedule (see table).

Fertilizer application at the recommended dose and integration of fertilizer N with GM proved superior to the control. Basal application of 7.5 t *G. maculata* with 25 kg urea N ha⁻¹ was on par with 100 kg urea N ha⁻¹ in terms of yield. Costs of cultivation, gross returns, net returns, and benefit-cost ratio of this integrated N management treatment were comparable with those of the recommended dose. With this treatment, a savings of 75 kg urea N ha⁻¹ may be achieved. ■

Fertilizer management— inorganic sources

Response of late-transplanted rice to NPK under irrigated conditions

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Rice followed by rapeseed - mustard is the most feasible double cropping system in Kashmir Valley (1650 m asl). But aberrant weather conditions (low temperature and cloudiness) delay transplanting. The NPK requirement of a crop under such a situation may differ from that of a timely planted rice crop, which usually requires 80-45-20 kg NPK ha⁻¹.

We conducted a 2-yr field trial at SKUAST's Shalimar Campus, on silty clay loam soil (pH 6.8, low available N and P, medium available K) during the 1990-91 wet seasons. The 18 treatments, tested in a randomized block design experiment with three replications, comprised different combinations of NPK levels (see table). Half the N and a full P and K dose were applied basally while the remaining N was applied in two splits: at tillering (18 d after transplanting [DAT]) and at panicle initiation (37 DAT).

Rice variety K39 was transplanted at 15 × 1.5-cm spacing at 3 seedlings per hill by the 1st week of Jul. During the experiment, temperatures ranged from 23.0 to 31.1 °C (maximum) and from 11.3 to 19.6 °C (minimum). Relative humidity was 45-76%. Total rainfall averaged 234 mm, spread over 35 d.